

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Design and Simulation of a Renewable Energy – Solar Powered - Tobacco Curing System

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Abstract

Tobacco, colloquially termed the golden leaf, contributes, significantly, towards sustaining the Zimbabwean economy, wherein its annual contribution to the Gross Domestic Product – through substantial revenue and exports earnings - had averaged more than 10% for a period stretching more than five decades to date. Production, curing and processing flue cured tobacco in Zimbabwe is substantially energy demanding. The principal energy sources utilised in the mercantile tobacco processing, in Zimbabwe, are coal, wood and grid electricity. Wood is the main source of energy used in the tobacco curing process in the country side farms where deforestation acceleration is reported to be a major problem attributable to tobacco processing, in those regions where there is no alternative fuel, to wood, for curing the golden leaf. This study present the results of a proposed design of renewable energy (solar energy) fuelled tobacco curing system in a barn for bulk tobacco curing. The designed system utilises solar thermal collectors to generate the heat energy for physical curing of the tobacco and accumulating thermal storage reservoir during the day. The design of the automated solar-powered tobacco curing system aims to provide a sustainable and cost-effective solution for tobacco farmers by reducing their reliance on non-efficient traditional curing methods that rely on fossil fuels and the use of extensive manual labour. The automated system is designed to optimise energy use and minimise costly wood use and manual intervention by utilising an Arduino Uno controller for automated system elements actuation. The design prototype simulation results are promising.

Keywords: Solar Radiation; Design Efficiency; Parabolic Collector; Modularity; Sustainable Energy; Renewable Energy

1. Introduction

Utilisation of renewable energy resources to address the energy demand challenge has reached peak priority consideration in human societies the world over [1], and indeed in the Zimbabwean farming community in particular, in their quest to achieve and secure a sustainable energy transition during the curing of tobacco in the production season. This research designed a solar energy powered, micro grid for driving the thermal energy system in the uninterrupted continuous batch bulk drying of flue cured tobacco, enabled by an integrated renewable thermal energy storage system. Flat plate solar thermal collectors were used to circulate hot air through the bulk drying tobacco barn during the day whilst the parabolic solar thermal collector is used to concentrate solar thermal energy onto the rock bed thermal energy storage system, for use in the tobacco barn hot air circulation during the night.

Tobacco, colloquially termed the golden leaf, contributes, significantly, towards sustaining the Zimbabwean economy, wherein its annual contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) – through substantial revenue and exports earnings - had averaged more than 10% for a period stretching more than five decades to date, [2]. Table 1 show a

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snippet of the tobacco crop GDP contribution to be the Zimbabwean economy in the recent past few years over a few conveniently selected years.

Table 1 Tobacco crop contribution to the Zimbabwe economy GDP

Year	GDP contribution in the Economy %
2000	8.2
2008	24.2
2016	11
2018	10
2020	10
2021	10
2022	10
2023	2.4
2024	5.44

It is apparent that tobacco has a significant contribution to the Zimbabwe economy, despite the observed attendant challenges of deforestation from the cutting down of trees for firewood to fuel the tobacco curing barns. Projectedly this tobacco influence shall continue to occur for a foreseeable future Thus, energy resources use optimisation strategies [3] and methodologies have to be developed in the tobacco processing business.

Producing, curing, and processing of tobacco is energy demanding, [4, 5]. The principal energy sources utilised in the business of tobacco processing, in the developing economies, are coal, wood and grid electricity. Deforestation is a major challenge in tobacco producing areas where no fuel substitute, to firewood, is available for use during tobacco curing. Figure 1 typifies the nature of deforestation occurring in the Zimbabwe tobacco farmlands where wood is used as the main fuel for curing tobacco.

Figure 1 Extensive deforestation prompted by wood cutting for tobacco curing [6]

The Zimbabwe flue cured tobacco processing enterprise, is dominated by the use of firewood fuel and this significantly contribute to the challenge of deforestation in the farming lands where wood is the main fuel driving the curing energy

[7]. Figure 2 shows the remarkable thermal insolation map of Zimbabwe. The map shows promising potential for solar energy utilisation in the country due to its wide spread availability across the greater part of the country.

Figure 2 Countrywide solar irradiation resource map of Zimbabwe [8]

The other forms of energy fuel, rarely, used in the advanced farms are coal and grid electricity, [9]. The report on coal use in tobacco curing show that it brings the challenges of combustion instability, which results in elevated energy consumption, hence expensive, and poses environmental pollution [10]. The use of firewood and manual labour for tobacco curing is expensive and unsustainable and could be mitigated by the creation and utilisation of alternative renewable energy systems. In concurrence with this observation, Shati, et al., [6] asserted that there is now imperative need to shifting away from the use of fire wood as the main fuel energy source utilised in curing tobacco. The same research reported on the unanimous supportive stance among tobacco farming interest stakeholders, surveyed, on the requirement of the pursuit of implementation of renewable sustainable energy system solutions in the tobacco curing facilities. Thus, the design in this study was inspired by the requirement to minimally contribute towards reducing the current tobacco-curing fire-wood-cutting driven deforestation and contributing towards fostering long term sustainability in the business of tobacco curing.

In an effort to tackle the elevated tobacco curing costs, a solar energy driven automated bulk tobacco curing barn system was designed, modelled and simulated to confirm the thermal energy distribution profile of the curing barn system. The potential application utility of solar energy in agro-processing systems of fresh cash crops is increasing, [11] in the recent times due to the affordability of solar technology resources. This design study investigated the technical practicability of utilising solar energy generated hot air to thermally cure tobacco in a bulk tobacco curing barn. The evolution of the microcomputer technology, in the recent past, offered increased feasibility of automating and controlling solar energy driven agricultural produce processing operations by utilising micro-controllers, [4, 12]. Performance optimisation and thermal efficiency of the system are anticipated to be realised through precise solar-energy based heat supply automatic control of the curing operation through employing the micro-computer control technology.

Tobacco is an extremely labor-intensive cash crop when compared to most crops grown locally. The tobacco flue-curing process involves heating and drying tobacco leaves and the process requires 43 m³ of fuel wood of 15 000 kg to produce an average of 1 400 kg and therefore high labor for cutting down trees for firewood and supplying of wood into the furnace [13]. Domestic labor for tobacco production and curing is expensive making up about 50% of the total cost [14]. The tobacco is allowed to dry over a period between one to eight weeks, therefore during this period there should be more labour input to continuously supply firewood into the barn for maintaining the optimum temperatures required in the drying chamber. The inability to mechanise such a complex operation that eliminates the tobacco curing optimum temperature maintenance problem, as well as the use of firewood, is a key solution point for the large labor requirements in tobacco production.

The country, Zimbabwe, has 4,130,000 hectares of arable land, with animal and manual draught power used to cultivate 25% of it. A significant part of the population are farmers who dependent on tobacco farming for their livelihoods [15]. Among the major cash crops that are exported from Zimbabwe, tobacco, the golden leaf, contributes the highest foreign currency earnings from the agricultural sector, dominating 50% of the total income from overall agricultural exports [16]. Though the industry is lucrative, it still lacks an automated solar system for tobacco curing to increase the quality of cured tobacco, the efficiency of the barn curing process system - through energy sustainability - and decrease labour intensity which are drawbacks to the industry’s operations.

Figure 3 show the minimum time taken to completely cure a leaf of tobacco using direct or indirect heating relative to the temperatures involved per each stage. The flue tobacco curing process uses 43 m³ of fuel wood of 15 000kg and produces an average of 1 400kg of cured tobacco [13]. Using a rocket barn the ratio of firewood to cured tobacco is 9 kg : 1 kg respectively. The indirect (flue-curing) process lasts for at least 200 hours to completely cure a leaf of tobacco whilst direct (fire) tobacco curing last for at least 270 hours to completely cure a leaf of tobacco, [2] . Despite the large amounts of firewood being used, the lack of automation and non-manual monitoring systems increases the time for curing and makes the system job very hard.

Figure 3 Tobacco curing process [9]

Figure 4 shows that monitoring and control are very crucial in tobacco curing for the best quality and good grade of tobacco. Temperature and humidity or moisture of both the leaf and surrounding of the leaf should be monitored thoroughly at each stage of the curing process.

Figure 4 Temperature against humidity during curing [9]

In much of the world, awareness is growing about renewable energy technologies having a major role in the extension of technologies to farmers in developing countries to improve their productivity [17]. The development of a reliable, fairly air-blown automatic solar system that can be mass-produced and used for tobacco curing would greatly aid the introduction of clean natural energy for tobacco curing.

Apart from the prevention of deforestation, land degradation, and air pollution, introducing a solar tobacco curing system that is automatically controlled will also reduce curing time as it eliminates human error in trying to maintain the optimum temperatures in the drying chamber. Due to the use of fire for curing tobacco leaves will always be smelling smoke from the fire burning but introducing this proposed solar energy-based curing system will eliminate this contamination factor and enhance the final leaf quality of the tobacco. Compared with a direct curing barn, the energy-saving rate can reach up to 50% when compared to the current curing regime [18]. Therefore, a heating source like an automated solar heat pump is projected to be more energy-efficient than direct firewood based natural airflow heating. It could have a non-negotiable, significant role to play in the advancement of sustainable use of energy.

1.1. Tobacco Curing

Tobacco curing is a deliberate controlled man-made effort intent on creating a favourable condition for the tobacco leaf to biologically physically mature. The two key goals targeted, are firstly, in the curing of tobacco relate to the provision of temperature and humidity conditions that will promote the subsistence of the physical biological and chemical changes occurring in the tobacco leaves, and secondly, timeous dehydration of the tobacco leaves so that they are preserved, [7]. The process is typically aimed at developing three key quality aspects of the tobacco, viz, the aroma, the colour and enzymatic changes in the tobacco leaf.

Tobacco curing methodology involves the removal of chlorophyll from the tobacco leaves, causing them to turn yellow (see the leaf colour change transitions shown in Figure 5). According to tobacco handling personnel, colour accounts for 75% of the market value of tobacco. This is a process which is carried out at a temperature range of 30-40°C from an elevated humidity level of 85%, [11]. Tobacco leaves are dried or cured when heat is distributed uniformly inside a tightly closed barn using a heat exchanger at a temperature of 40-50°C, and finally, the main leaf stem is dried by exposing the tobacco to a higher barn temperature of 65-70°C with declining humidity for a determinate time duration, [19]. The leaves are loosely hung inside the barn to allow for an easy flow of hot air. Natural convection is the primary mode of heat transfer to the leaves. Wood, coal, solar energy, and LP gas are all common fuels used in curing tobacco, [2]. Figures 5 depict the three clear views of the fundamental curing process stages taken by the tobacco leaf during the curing process, [20].

Figure 5 Three stages of tobacco curing [20]

There are four curing processes namely

- **Flue or indirect curing-** The barns' flues come from furnaces or fireboxes that are fed externally throughout the curing process. These fireboxes are employed to provide heat without exposing the tobacco to smoke for curing in the barn [20]. The tobacco that is produced has a high sugar content and medium to high nicotine levels.
- **Fire or direct curing-** Tobacco is strung in vast barns, and a constant fire of wood, coal, or charcoal is maintained burning beneath the tobacco. The tobacco produced has a low sugar content and a high nicotine content [21].
- **Sun curing-** Involves exposing tobacco directly to the sun until the leaves are brown and withered. The tobacco produced is low in both sugar and nicotine [19].
- **Air curing-** Tobacco is hung in a well-ventilated barn and allowed to dry over a period of four to eight weeks. The tobacco produced is low in sugar, high in nicotine, and has a sweet flavour [21].

1.2. Solar heat collectors

There are numerous types of solar collectors. Solar heat collectors are classified as either stationary or non-concentrating and concentrating. A list of the numerous subcategories and traits of thermal energy collectors is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Solar energy collectors

Motion	Collector type	Absorber shape	Concentration ratio	Indicative temperature range °C
Stationary	Flat plate collector (ETC)	Flat	1	30-80
	Evacuated tube collector (ETC)	Flat	1	50-200
	Compound parabolic collector (CPC)	Flat	1-15	60-200
		Tubular	10-40	80-300
Single-axis tracking	Linear Fresnel reflector (LFR)	Tubular	15-45	80-250
	Parabolic trough collector (PTC)	Tubular	10-50	80-300
	Parabolic trough collector (PTC)	Tubular	100-1000	80-300
	Cylindrical trough collector (CTC)	Tubular	100-1500	100-500
Two axis tracking	Parabolic dish reflector (PDR)	Point	100-1500	150-2000
	Heliostat field collector (HFC)	Point	100-1500	150-2000

Courtesy: [22]

The flat-plate solar collector is a device used to convert solar energy into thermal energy. It consists of a box-like structure with glass sheets covering the top surface [22]. The glass transmits shortwave solar irradiation but increases the glass temperature by trapping long-wave radiation within it. This trapped radiation is then absorbed by the surface absorbent, which is usually made of a material with high thermal conductivity such as copper or aluminium. The absorber plate heats up and transfers its heat to a fluid that flows through it, which can be water, air or some other fluid depending on the application. Durability, energy transmission, non-degradability, and strength are all important characteristics. According to research findings reported by Himanshu, et al., [23], a larger component of solar irradiance energy impinging on a transparent-material-covered blackened surface of high absorbency behaviour, is transmitted into the transportation media in the pipes and gets conveyed to the storage or use point. Figure 6 shows a typical schematic image of a flat plate solar collector. This was considered in the curing barn design for the portion responsible for direct heating air supply feeder line into the barn during the day.

Figure 6 Flat plate solar collector [24]

1.3. Solar thermal energy storage

Thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, and heat capacity of materials are all important properties in determining the efficiency of a thermal system, [25]. Thermal energy storage is one of the utmost effective methods of warehousing astral energy when a fluid (air, water or other media) is incorporated into contact with solar air heater. Thermal energy accumulation facilities enable the collection and accumulation of solar energy systems for utilisation in the convenient future [23]. This technology enhances flexibility and efficiency, in operation processes, by storing the heat energy for eventual uses as may be deemed convenient by the users, [26, 27]. Thermal accumulation (storage) systems exterminate intermittent energy status between the supply and demand sides. Solar energy storage system could be stored as sensible or latent heat, where respectively, the thermal energy could be stored inside the storage medium by raising the storing body temperature which does not change its material phase, [23], whereas, in latency form the stored energy causes the storing body phase to change its state. According to Clerjon and Perdu [26], solar energy based thermal energy storage systems accumulate thermal energy into the thermal storage material before sunset and the thermal energy shall be used to heat the material at a later time even after the sun had long set. Currently thermal storage systems are integrated to accumulate thermal energy for use in greenhouses, [23]. The schematic representation process chain, illustrated in Figure 7 denotes the conversion principle of energy from solar irradiation to usable and storage warehousable thermal energy. Irradiance – the insolation energy in the electromagnetic wave form per unit surface area of the earth measured in kW/m^2 - is the key fundamental factor enabling the utility of solar thermal energy system application, [6].

Figure 7 Solar irradiance to thermal energy conversion process schematic representation chain [28]

In light of the abundance, of solar energy availability in Zimbabwe, during the tobacco curing season, the objective of this research included designing and analysing the performance of the solar thermal energy tobacco bulk curing system, wherein solar energy heated hot air is circulated through the curing ban to provide tobacco curing process as desired.

The amount of heat energy (Q) transferred, balance for short term and long-term storage requirements during an insolation exposure process, is given by equation 1, thus:

$$mc_p \frac{\delta T}{\delta t} = Q_u - Q_L - Q_s \quad (1)$$

Where, m - the mass; C_p - its specific heat; T - the temperature; t - the time; Q_u - solar energy rate which charges the storage; Q_L - the energy rate required by a curing barn; and Q_s is the energy loss rate to the surroundings, then also

$$Q_u = I_a \quad (2)$$

Where, I_a - actual solar insolation

The collector efficiency is given by equation 3, thus:

$$\eta = \frac{Q_n}{Q} = a(1 - g) - C \frac{\Delta T}{Q} \quad (3)$$

Where, Q - where solar radiation density normal to the collector plate (W/m^2); Q_n - net heat absorption (W/m^2), g - reflection and absorption loss in the cover plate; a - absorption coefficient for solar radiation of a black body; T_{pl} - absorber surface/black plate temperature (K); T_{gl} - surrounding air/glass cover temperature (K); $g = 0.15$; $a = 0.09$

The projected profile of daily insolation curve and the associated solar insolation collector efficiency is represented in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Summer time daily insolation curve and collector efficiency estimate, [6]

The useful energy gain by the collector, under steady state, is given by equation 4:

$$q_u = F_R A_c [(\tau\alpha)I - U_L(T_i - T_a)] \quad (4)$$

Where, $\tau\alpha$ - is the absorbance transmittance product; U_L - is the overall heat transfer coefficient (J/m^2K); T_i - Temperature at inlet; L - is the bed length (m); F_R - Collector removal factor.

The long-established sensible heat storage computation formula, which makes use of a variety of common materials, wherein, the mode of thermal energy transfer is by conduction through heat exchangers, is summarised in equation 5, [29].

$$q = mc_p(T_f - T_i) \quad (5)$$

Where, m - the mass (given by equation 6); C_p - its specific heat; T_f - final temperature; T_i - initial temperature,

And,

$$m = \frac{V}{\rho} \quad (6)$$

Wherein, V - volume, and ρ - density

Therefore,

$$q = \frac{V}{\rho} c_p (T_f - T_i) \quad (7)$$

Heat capacity (ρc_p), is the combination of density and specific heat, and in order to store solar energy in another medium, the thermal conductivity of that medium is also important, leading to the parameter known as thermal diffusivity [5], which is in equation 8:

$$\frac{k}{\rho c_p} \quad (8)$$

The energy storage materials performance behaviour depends on the heat capacity and thermal diffusivity, [23, 30]. Table 3 shows common storage materials.

Table 3 Properties of some common heat storage material

Storage material	Specific heat, c_p	Density, ρ	Temperature T	Heat capacity, ρc_p	Thermal diffusivity, $k/\rho c_p$
Air (at P_0)	0.2415	0.0012	20	0.0003	—
Asbestos	0.2500	0.1500	—	0.0375	0.0083
Alcohol	0.55-0.65	0.8000	0-40	0.4800	0.0009
Brine	0.7090	1.2000	0	0.8508	0.0026
Brick	0.2000	1.7000	21	0.3400	0.0033
Charcoal	0.2420	0.4000	0-70	0.0968	0.0170
Concrete	0.2000	2.2000	21	0.4400	0.0082
Glass	0.16-0.20	2.515	—	0.4527	0.0045
Ice	0.5000	0.9180	-1 to -21	0.1836	0.0292
Porcelain	0.2550	2.3000	15-1000	0.5865	0.0041
Rock	0.2100	2.5600	20	0.5400	0.1416
Sand (dry)	0.1910	1.6000	—	0.3056	0.0026
Steel	0.1200	7.8500	0–200	0.9420	0.1243
Water	1.000	1.0000	4	1.0000	0.0014
Wood (oak)	0.5700	0.7700	0-70	0.4389	0.00113

Courtesy: ([30, 23, 28])

The design concepts used in this research considered the behaviour of these respective materials in the selection of the energy retention bed for the powering of the curing barn.

1.3.1. Rock bed thermal storage

Packed pebble (rock) beds commonly, epitomise the supreme sustainable storage system components for accumulating solar thermal energy during the irradiation day time intended for use of the heated hot air during the night time of the day. The heat stowage component receive the thermal energy accumulation from the collector unit during the sun shining day period and releases it into the curing barn during the evening rock pebble bed heat discharging process. The core critical parameters which were monitored during the design of the hard heavy rock solar heat energy storage bed included spherical pebble diameter in which the solid to void ratio was maintained at 58:42 percent; length of the bed; the collector surface area airflow per unit area rate and frontal area of the bed [31]. The energy storage bed was appropriately designed and sized with full consideration of the key factors, viz: the thermal load, the collector, inter alia [32].

Rock bed thermal storage is a unique method of warehousing thermal energy using a bed of rocks as a medium. Hot air is passed through the bottom of the rock bed, which heats up the rocks. As cold air is introduced from the top, it passes through the large plenum and creates a thermocline, where natural convection takes place [33]. The pressure drop created by this process allows for airflow direction to be controlled without the need for a blower or pump which would entail additional pumping costs. Buoyancy effects also play a role in creating sectional areas within the rock bed that allow for efficient heat transfer, [29]. Figure 9 shows a typical view of rock bed thermal storage. The Hughes' method was used to model the thermal performance. The method involves thermal radiation, thermal conduction, and natural convection, which work together to optimize the thermal performance of the system. The inter-particle spaces within the rock bed allow for dimensional fluid flow, while the sloping edge creates sectional areas that enhance heat transfer. Particle diameter also plays a role in determining the core region where heat is stored.

Due to the fact that crushed rock is irregular and non-uniform, the particle diameter must be defined. The particle diameter D_v in this study is the average volume-equivalent sphere diameter, for n samples of volume V_{pi} , was computed from equation 9.

Figure 9 Rock bed thermal storage [34]

The thermal capacity of rock bed pebbles is substantially lower than that of water, yet the density level is superior, thus, consequently the pebble bed heat storage is a more efficient means of thermal energy accumulation for eventual use, nonetheless [35].

$$D_v = \left(\frac{6}{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{i=1}^n V_{pi} \right] \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (9)$$

The Hughes method uses a simplified Nusselt number correlation for air-rock beds, [34], calculated from equation 10.

$$Nu_v = \left(\frac{hD_v}{k} \right) = Re_{pv}^{0.6} \quad (10)$$

Where, h - is the coefficient of surface-area heat transfer; k - the thermal conductivity of air; and Re_{pv} - the Reynolds number defined by the fluid viscosity μ and mass flux G through the packed bed, equation 11,

$$Re_{pv} = \left(\frac{GD_v}{\mu} \right) \quad (11)$$

Rock bed inlet and outlet temperature functions profiles, used to control the air flow, are depicted in Figure 10, [34]. Rock bed air can be charged or discharged through the bed outlet or inlet, respectively, and air outlet temperatures are monitored to ensure efficient operation.

A

B

Figure 10 Rock bed air outlet temperature profile during (a) charging and (b) discharging [34]

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Detailed Design and Development

The innovative systematic Pahl and Bertz design approach process [36] was employed in developing the iterative design concepts generated in this design task process, through incremental design improvement - of the tobacco barn, curing and heating system physical hardware configuration of components, as well as the system control architecture. Three concepts, which were the conceived design ideas of the design product – the curing barn, the drive energy conversion process and the control process - were respectively generated for each of the designed system components based on the overall expected system performance parameter requirements. The Pugh matrix concept scoring and screening process [37] was used to filter and prioritise the selection of the most promising design idea, in accordance with the set out prioritisation algorithmic protocol, so as to pick the best likely performing concept in each respect as referenced to the expected system performance criteria.

The selected concepts were further developed and improved by refining the design constraints through computation of various requisite component sizes and equipment integral to the design. These calculations are essential for determining the appropriate sizes of materials and equipment required for development. Additionally, the calculations aided in specifying components, ensuring their alignment with the design goals and objectives. The primary objective of this design activity was to establish precise material and component specifications to support the project's successful execution.

The curing barn simulation batch charge consisted of 110 kg mass of undried tobacco, at a humidity level of 85%, hung inside the sealed barn where controlled air circulation, at 40 kg/hour, subsisted. The traditional Zimbabwe tobacco curing process involves hanging tobacco leaves, in a controlled interior air circulating tobacco barn environment which is exterior air tight. The thermal and humidity controlled circulating air dehydrates the hung tobacco leaves. Dehydration of the tobacco commenced at the temperature of 35 °C and the temperature was gradually raised up to 60 °C, whilst simultaneously decreasing the tobacco leaves humidity which would be exhausted from the barn environment until it reached a decreased level of about 35%. The second curing cycle stage entailed gradually raising the barn interior environment temperature from 60 to 70 °C, during which temperature state the relative humidity also decrease to about 18%. The tobacco leaf midrib is dried to the physical model level in this stage, at the temperature of 70 °C and humidity of 18%. The full drying cycle of the 110 kg tobacco bulk batch consumed a measured energy amount of 302 MJ.

The features of the tobacco crop leaves used in the design test had the following features: an average leaf length of 62.85 cm, average width of 35.93 cm, leaf area of 1433.97 cm², average leaf length/width ratio of 1.759, leaf average thickness of 325 micrometres, midrib average transection area of 1.106 cm² and average transection area of vascular axis of 0.1126 cm².

Since mud is a considerably more effective heat insulator than bricks, the barn's insulation issues could be solved thus. This natural insulation material was less expensive. To transfer increasing amounts of heat from hot gases to the interior of the barn, the thermal energy supply pipes were made of material with the highest coefficient of heat transfer.

The cross sections of the solar collector through which the fluid flows have been selected based on a thermal study, [38]. The thermal collector area in this research was 2 panels of dimensions, respectively, 2 m x 1 m (constituting 4 m² area). This conformed to the recommendation that the height and width measurements should be in correspondence with tobacco leaves maximum average length and width [39] above. The amount of moisture contained in a material is articulated either in dry or wet basis as a percentage or decimal fraction value component of the full object weight, [28]. In the dry basis, the amount of moisture present in the tobacco leaf is computed from equation 12 and expressed as a percentage, thus:

$$M_{db} = \frac{W_o - W_d}{W_d} \times 100\% \quad (12)$$

The wet –based moisture content expresses the percent value of the weight of the moisture present in the product per given unit weight of the wet material. It is expressed thus, equation 13:

$$M_{wb} = \frac{W_o - W_d}{W_o} \times 100\% \quad (13)$$

Where, W_o represent the undried product weight in kg. W_d stands for the dried product weight in kg, M_{db} represents the mass of the dried product and M_{wb} represents the wet product weight in kg.

The thermal storage capacity of the rock bed required to store the excess thermal energy generated by the parabolic trough and the flat collector during the day was determined after considering various aspects of the thermal storage rock bed size was determined to be 3 m length x 1 m width x 1 m depth, making the volume of the rock bed of 3 m³. The thermal storage capacity was computed to be 237,734 kJ from the application of equation 14.

Thermal storage capacity = Volume x Specific heat capacity x Density x Temp change (14)

$$Q = mC\Delta T \quad (14)$$

Where, Q - the heat energy required in joules; m - the mass of air in the barn, C - the air's specific heat capacity'; and ΔT - the temperature difference between the physical model temperature and the ambient temperature. Mass, m can be determined from equation 15.

$$m = \rho v \quad (15)$$

Where, ρ - the air density and v - is the volume of the barn.

To calculate the mass of the rocks in the rock bed thermal storage system that can provide heating during the night (12 hours), there was need to first compute the heat energy required to maintain the physical system temperature in the curing barn over the 12-hour period. For a curing barn volume of 175 m³ (5 m x 5 m x7 m being the barn dimensions) and a maximum physical model temperature of 70 °C, the total heat energy required to maintain this temperature for 12 hours is calculated as explained in the following.

The mass of rocks of the thermal storage rock bed system (3,183 kg), was determined with consideration of the thermal energy capacity of the rock bed material and the physical model temperature range, which was maximum heating temperature of 75 °C and 15 °C minimum anticipated ambient temperature during the period with operational factor of safety taken into account, considered in applying equation 16.

$$m = \frac{Q_T}{C\Delta T\rho} \quad (16)$$

The detailed design results are presented in the ensuing.

3. Detailed design development and simulation results

3.1. Physical System design results

This section provides a detailed description of the size, specifications, and components required for the realisation of the automated tobacco curing barn system. Components and parameter sizing was established in the background of applying extensive design calculations as per the standard engineering component sizing practice. Design calculations were relevant towards ensuring accuracy in all aspects of the curing barn design development.

The detailed design of the tobacco curing system configuration of components designed, after a number of design iterations, in the curing system is shown in the schematic arrangement of components in Figure 11. The system functionality goes thus, during the day, the flat plate collector is used to provide direct thermal energy to the barn, while the parabolic trough is used to heat the thermal storage unit and store the excess energy for later use during the evening. The control unit automatically regulates the tobacco barn interior temperature conditions. This final selected design combines the cost-effectiveness and ease of implementation of the controlled tobacco curing process with the thermal storage capability as shown in Figure11 and Figure 12.

An automated control system is used to switch between the flat plate collector and the thermal storage depending on the time of day and the energy requirements of the barn. This approach would allow for maximum energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness while ensuring that the barn is always supplied with the necessary thermal energy.

Shati, et al. [28] suggested a curing system, supported with an environmental-friendly auxiliary thermal energy source and astral photovoltaic for drives and controls is piquantly advocated, for the golden leaf curing green energy installations in Zimbabwe.

Figure 11 Solar thermal tobacco curing system schematic layout

The full designed tobacco curing system pictorial components configuration arrangements is shown in Figure 12. The flat plate collector dimensions were determined from the computation of equation 17, thus, giving a total required effective collection area of 4.79 m² after factoring in several intermediate parameter conversion computations.

$$\text{Solar collector size} = \frac{Q_T + \text{Heat Loss}}{\text{Solar radiation} \times \text{Efficiency}} \quad (17)$$

Figure 12 Solar thermal system pictorial layout

The selected flat plate collector, in the designed system, comprised of an absorber plate, a transparent cover, and insulation. The sun's radiation is absorbed by the absorber plate, which is painted in a dull colour and shaped in a zigzag pattern, increasing the surface area for absorption, allowing the greater quantity of heat to be absorbed and improving the heat transfer efficiency. The transparent cover allows the solar energy to enter while protecting the absorber plate from the elements, and the insulation at the back of the collector helps to keep the heat within.

The size of the parabolic trough required to heat the thermal storage unit during the day was determined, by calculation considering thermal storage capacity and insolation efficiency, to be of size 4.32 m². This was determined as parabola trough size required to deliver thermal energy amounting to 130.735 MJ required to accumulate heat energy in the storage rock bed system.

Figure 13 Control diagram

Figure 14 System parameters regulation control circuit design elements

Another critical component for this barn's ability to perform the intended functions is the automated solar-powered curing system control, which includes an electronic component. The design was fundamentally concerned with the innovation of temperature, humidity control, and other wireless control mechanisms such as GSM communication circuitry as regards the functioning behaviour of the curing barn. The design used the less costly Arduino Uno instead of the expensive PLC circuitry to power the system control in the simulation iteration runs. The Arduino Uno was chosen as a good PLC substitute, in simulation, due to its low cost, numerous input/output pins, and general-purpose pins for

a variety of applications, as well as its high processing speed. Figure 13 shows the control system, design concept, of the automated solar-powered tobacco curing system.

The circuit design presented, in Figure 14, depicts the connections for all of the electronic components that constitute the automated solar powered tobacco barn curing system control.

3.2. System functionality simulation and modelling results

The barn prototype model was constructed. The prototype was developed using different tools, keeping the design objectives in mind. Samples, of tobacco, were dried in the barn and measurements, of the drying process, were recorded. The barn curing process was also simulated and results were recorded and compared, of the simulation model as well as the physical model curing process. The tobacco barn heat distribution simulation was performed to quantify the variability of temperature and humidity within the curing barn, which influences the tobacco leaf quality. Figure 15 shows the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation planning flow chart of the tobacco curing barn heating process. The control system pseudo code text instructions is detailed in Appendix 1.

Figure 15 Design CFD simulation plan flow diagram of the solar energy curing system

Figure 16 results show the thermal distribution gradient map simulation of the interior environment of the curing barn. It is apparent, from the heat distribution map that the heat energy reasonably saturates the barn’s interior such as to cause the dehydration of the tobacco hung inside it adequately.

Figure 16 Curing barn interior thermal map system simulation

The heat distribution simulation was performed to quantify the variability of temperature, within the curing barn, which influences the distribution of tobacco leaf quality. The simulation results for a five-day curing schedule is presented in Figure 17(a) whilst results presented in Figure 17(b) show the relative humidity variation inside the curing barn during the same period. The temperature variation results indicate the adequacy of the temperature elevation within the barn to the maximum soaking temperature of 70 °C required to cause the drying of the leaf midrib after the main leaf body which dries sufficiently at lower temperatures.

Figure 17 (a) Curing temperature and (b) relative humidity, respectively, vs time plots

The relative humidity change, of the curing barn interior shown in Figure 17(b) indicate good drying capacity of the designed curing barn system as reflected by the comparability of the live curing and simulation curing humidity reduction curves over the assessment time period of 5 days.

Comparison graphs for six days drying curing process schedule results, graphically presented in Figure 18(a) graphs, respectively, of the physical model temperature and simulated system temperature, as well as the physical model humidity and simulated system humidity, results shown in Figure 18(b).

Figure 18 (a) Curing temperature and (b) relative humidity, respectively, vs time plots

Graph results presented in Figure 18(b) show the comparative curves of the simulated and practical (physical model) profiles of relative humidity over a six-day curing schedule.

3.3. Solar driven tobacco curing system design implementation costs

This section deals with project costing. It is carried out to evaluate the costs associated with project implementation in order to assess the financial feasibility of project implementation. It involves an analysis of various components and economic evaluation to ensure financial feasibility. Economic evaluation of the solar energy systems design is implemented in order to establish the least expenditure of providing the sustainable renewable energy-based tobacco curing system. The costing details of implementing the prototype development are presented in Appendices 2 and 3. The project implementation cost is estimated at US\$1300.00 and the payback period is two (2) years.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, the development of an automated solar-powered tobacco curing system represents a viable solution for long-term and cost-effective curing process in tobacco production. The design limitation though is in the design process assuming that there shall not be extended periods of overcast cloud cover weather patterns during the tobacco curing periods when extensive energy resources shall be required. The design research strives to strengthen farmers' capability in harnessing the renewable solar energy and storing the energy for continued use in curing tobacco during periods when there is no clear sunshine. This is anticipated to benefit the farmers, through increasing the efficiency in tobacco curing. Further work relate to building more real-life prototypes and carrying out more tests and gathering more data for easier of future predictions.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors were not conflicted and had no conflict to declare.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Software Design: Pseudo Code for automated tobacco curing barn process control

Among the three areas of this design, the software design for an automated solar-powered tobacco curing barn is the most critical. Software is the brain that instructs the system to meet the specified parameters. Several factors were carefully considered to ensure that the software operates flawlessly. The designers used the knowledge base of tobacco expert curers as a reliable parametric source to design the software. Arduino Uno was chosen to carry out the required controller operations. This section of the design also received presentations from all relevant algorithms. In some cases, pseudo codes were also provided to assist with the proper design and programming of the specific automated solar-

powered tobacco curing barn operation. The entire code was developed in the in C++ language, to implement the set of instructions texturally presented in the section's headings below

4.1. Leaf colouring stage

- If the temperature is less than 30 °C, turn on the fan to raise the temperature.
- If the temperature is between 30-40 °C, turn off all actuators while rotating the leaf hangers once every one-hour interval.
- If the temperature exceeds 40 °C, turn on the blower and the heat reduction fan, and turn on the motor to rotate the leaf hanger while the heat increasing fan is turned off.
- If the humidity level in the barn is less than 70%, open the valve to increase moisture in the barn and turn on the motor to rotate the leaf hanger every 1-hour interval.
- If the humidity level exceeds 75%, turn on all actuators to reduce moisture while maintaining motor rotation and temperature.

4.2. Lamina drying stage

- If the temperature is less than 40 °C, turn on the fan to raise the temperature in the curing barn.
- If the temperature is between 40 °C and 60°C, turn off all actuators while the motor is running to rotate the leaf hangers every 1 hour.
- If the temperature exceeds 60 °C, turn on the blower and the heat reduction fan, and turn on the motor to rotate the leaf hanger while the heat increasing fan is turned off.
- If the humidity level in the barn chamber falls below 30%, turn on the valve to maintain the humidity level while maintaining the hanger rotation.
- If the humidity level exceeds 35%, turn on all actuators and rotate the leaf hanger every 1 hour.

4.3. Stem drying

- If the temperature is less than 60 °C, turn on the heat blower to raise the temperature in the curing barn.
- If the temperature is between 60-70 °C, turn off the actuators while rotating the motor for the leaf hangers once every one-hour interval.
- If the temperature rises above 70 °C, turn on the blower and fan while the motor of the leaf hanger remains turned on.
- If the humidity level is below 20%, turn on the valve while the leaf hangers continue to rotate once every one-hour interval.
- If the humidity level reaches 18%, turn on the buzzer to indicate curing cycle completion and maintain the leaf hanger in rotation.

Appendix 2

Table Bill of materials

Qty	Item Description	Price	Total Cost (US\$)
5m ²	Transparent glazing	\$ 2.10	\$ 10.50
5m ²	Absorber plate	\$ 100.00	\$ 500.00
4	Light Dependent Resistor (LDR)	\$ 1.25	\$ 5.00
1	Legging insulation	\$ 50.00	\$ 50.00
2	Servo motor	\$ 5.00	\$ 10.00
1	Geared motor	\$ 30.00	\$ 30.00
10	Light Emitting Diode (LED)	\$ 0.20	\$ 2.00
1	Breadboard	\$ 6.00	\$ 6.00
2	DHT11 Humidity and Temperature Sensor	\$ 6.00	\$ 12.00

1	Arduino Nano	\$ 15.00	\$ 15.00
1	Arduino Wemos D1 Wifi Uno ESP8266	\$ 25.00	\$ 25.00
1	Arduino power supply	\$ 10.00	\$ 10.00
1	Push button	\$ 1.00	\$ 1.00
1	Fan	\$ 6.00	\$ 6.00
1	Buzzer	\$ 1.00	\$ 1.00
1	Jumper cables	\$ 5.00	\$ 5.00
1	Housing Materials	\$ 200.00	\$ 2000.00
	Total		\$ 898.50

Appendix 3

Table Total cost estimation

Expenditure description	Total cost (US\$)
Total Material Costs	\$ 898.00
Total Labour Costs	\$ 280.00
Overhead Costs	\$ 122.00
Total Capital Investment Cost	\$ 1300.00